

ACCESS Technical Landscape Assessment: High-Performance Computing, Data, and Machine-Learning

We acknowledge the Traditional Owners of the land on which our research infrastructure and community operate across Australia and pay our respects to Elders past and present. We recognise the thousands of years of accumulated knowledge and deep connection they have with all the Earth systems we simulate.

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Executive Summary

High Performance Computing (HPC), data and machine learning (ML) capabilities are rapidly evolving, presenting both opportunities and challenges for climate and weather modelling. These challenges have significant implications for the Australian Community Climate and Earth System Simulator (ACCESS) and the broader research community that relies on ACCESS data outputs. As a national research infrastructure, ACCESS-NRI will play a critical role in supporting the community through this transition and ensuring Australia's climate modelling capability remains scalable, resilient and internationally competitive.

This document provides an assessment of the current technical landscape and examines how emerging developments in HPC, data practices, and ML may affect the future of ACCESS. It outlines key trends and pressures across these areas, highlighting where future work will be required to maintain scientific impact and stay at the cutting edge of weather and climate modelling.

Key Findings

- HPC architectures are shifting rapidly toward GPUs, requiring substantial updates to ACCESS model components to ensure future performance, portability, and scalability.
- Growing data volumes and increasingly complex workflows are straining storage, I/O, and data interoperability, with inconsistencies in metadata, formats and post-processing creating barriers to efficient analysis and reuse.
- Machine learning is advancing quickly but is currently limited by a disconnected community, infrastructure gaps, insufficient GPU capacity and lack of curated ML-ready datasets, all of which restrict the broader adoption of ML methods across the ACCESS community.

To support the ACCESS community, several priorities emerge from this assessment. First, preparing ACCESS model components for next-generation GPU-based HPC systems will be essential, both to maintain performance and to enable high-resolution modelling. Second, improving data interoperability and long-term usability will require embedding consistent metadata, provenance, and data specifications directly within the modelling workflows rather than relying on post-processing. Third, addressing growing pressure on data handling, including I/O performance, will require updated workflows to support scalable data analysis. Fourth, lowering barriers to data discovery, analysis and ML adoption will be important for broadening the impact of ACCESS outputs, particularly through user-friendly catalogues, compute-to-data approaches, and supporting ML-ready datasets. Finally, foster an effective, collaborative community of researchers and software engineers in the area of ML for climate and weather.

These trends indicate that coordinated planning and strategic investment will be needed across HPC, data, and ML domains. ACCESS-NRI is well placed to support this work in partnership with the broader Australian and international communities, helping to ensure Australia's climate modelling capability remains future-ready.

Context

Australia's climate simulator, ACCESS-NRI, is a national research infrastructure that aims to deliver a world-class Earth system modelling infrastructure to predict Australia's weather and climate. This requires significant computing resources, a diverse software ecosystem, and people with deep expertise in both research and technical domains. With technology evolving rapidly, the technical landscape and ACCESS-NRI strategies need to be continuously examined to maximise the utilisation of current resources and prepare for emerging trends. This landscape assessment document focuses on three key areas: (1) HPC & cloud computing, (2) data, and (3) Artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) techniques in climate and weather modelling.

This document provides an assessment of the current technical landscape and examines how emerging developments in HPC, data, and machine learning may affect the future of the ACCESS modelling system. It outlines key trends and highlights their implications for climate and weather modeling and where future work will be required. While this assessment is not exhaustive, it draws on the combined experience of the co-authors and insights gathered through community engagement, providing a perspective on some of the key challenges and opportunities most likely to affect ACCESS in the coming years.

High-Performance and Cloud Computing

A. Recent and Future Trends

The last 20 years have seen major changes in semiconductor advancements and microprocessor architecture trends. Since around 2005, microprocessor frequency has not increased significantly, and single-threaded performance has increased at a much slower pace than in previous decades. On the other hand, the number of transistors in a chip has kept increasing steadily at an almost constant rate. Better solid-state processes have allowed the creation of smaller logical cores and fit more cores per chip. These trends are reflected in the rapid development of increasingly powerful massively parallel processors, like Graphical Processing Units (GPUs), while improvements of traditional CPUs have occurred at a much lower pace.

Figure 1: Microprocessor trends over the past 50 years. Reproduced from <https://github.com/karlrupp/microprocessor-trend-data>. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

High Performance Computing (HPC) facilities rely heavily on the latest advancements in microprocessors to provide increasing computing power to their users. This means that, nowadays, the only viable route to replace existing HPC machines with significantly more powerful ones is to increase the number of available GPUs. The pace at which this change is occurring can be gauged by looking at the Top 500 of the most powerful computers in the world¹: the performance share provided by GPUs and similar accelerators went from 0% in 2005 to nearly 83% in November 2024. This trend is very likely to continue over the next few years.

¹ <https://www.top500.org>

These recent changes in HPC trends have, in turn, disrupted the development of scientific software designed to run on super-computers: techniques, tools and algorithms suitable for efficient execution on CPUs are not necessarily suitable when porting codes to GPUs. Scientific codes that support different architectures that want to leverage the performance advantage of GPU-vendor specific APIs and tools, have to balance the trade-offs between increasing code complexity and the performance benefits.

Cloud computing is another area where GPUs are steadily taking hold. As the number of cloud-based applications and their users keeps increasing, so does the need for computing power. One area driving this increase in demand is AI applications, including large-language models and machine-learning, which are particularly suitable for running on GPUs. As a result, cloud computing providers have been expanding their GPU-based facilities, with some of them, like the Eagle system from Microsoft Azure, now rivaling the largest HPC supercomputers in terms of computing power.

Another growing trend in cloud computing that might be relevant for climate and weather modelling is edge computing. Edge computing enhances data accessibility by processing data closer to its source, reducing latency, bandwidth dependency, and costs associated with data ingress and egress. Instead of relying solely on centralized cloud servers, edge computing enables real-time data analysis on local devices, gateways, or micro data centers. By decentralizing computation, edge computing can improve performance, enhance security, reduce costs, and ensure continuous access to critical data, even with limited cloud connectivity.

B. Opportunities and Challenges in Using GPUs

GPUs are part of a broader type of specialized hardware components, generically called accelerators, designed to offload and speed up specific types of computations from a CPU. Other types of accelerators include Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs), Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs), and Data Processing Units (DPUs). Although all are potentially useful for climate and weather modeling, only GPUs are readily available, nowadays and in the foreseeable future, in the Tier-1 HPC centers used by the ACCESS community.

GPUs differ from CPUs on several key architectural components. At its core, a GPU consists of Streaming Multiprocessors (SMs), which house thousands of shader cores that execute arithmetic operations in parallel. The memory hierarchy includes global memory (VRAM), which is large but relatively slow, shared memory, which is faster and accessible by cores within the same SM, and registers, which are the fastest and used for immediate computations. GPUs execute instructions in warps, groups of typically 32 threads that run in lockstep. This design allows GPUs to excel at highly parallel tasks, while relying on CPUs for sequential control and task scheduling. Another key difference is the increasing specialisation of GPUs to maximise the throughput of floating-point operations at lower precisions. Modern GPUs include dedicated compute units for different floating-point precisions, with a much smaller number of double-precision units when compared to lower precision units.

GPU's massive parallelism holds the promise of orders of magnitude increase in performance for computationally intensive applications such as climate models. These performance improvements can significantly reduce time to solution, enabling higher-resolution simulations and more

ensemble runs within the same computational budget. This, in turn, enhances the ability to capture small-scale processes, improve forecast accuracy, and provide more robust climate projections.

The architectural differences between CPUs and GPUs and the different APIs and software stacks mean that a code written for CPUs will need to be modified to run on GPUs. This porting of CPU codes can be very challenging, in particular for existing climate models that have been highly optimised for CPU-based architectures. Many of these models have been developed over decades with codebases written in Fortran, relying on assumptions about memory access patterns and parallelism that do not naturally map onto GPUs.

Furthermore, these models rely on double-precision arithmetic to maintain numerical stability, conserve physical quantities, and control error growth in long simulations. However, because modern GPUs deliver far higher performance in lower precisions, fully exploiting their capability would require adopting mixed-precision algorithms. Therefore, refactoring these models to efficiently utilize GPU parallelism often requires substantial rewriting, rethinking numerical algorithms, and addressing data movement between CPU and GPU memory.

There are currently three major GPU vendors catering for the HPC market: Nvidia, AMD and Intel. While NVIDIA, AMD, and Intel GPUs share similar designs and are used to achieve similar goals, each vendor provides its own application programming interface (API) and software stack, with varying cross-vendor support. This diversity of GPU hardware and software ecosystems adds a further layer of complexity. Climate model developers need to ensure portability across different GPU vendors but maintaining performance portability across these platforms challenges software development and requires ongoing support and testing. Furthermore, debugging and profiling performance bottlenecks on GPUs can be more difficult than on traditional CPUs, requiring specialised tools and expertise.

There are currently several programming frameworks for porting existing codes to GPUs or to write new codes with GPU support, each one involving tradeoffs in performance, portability, and porting effort:

Vendors APIs: In this approach, programmers write explicit GPU kernels using existing APIs, like CUDA and HIP. This low-level approach has the advantage of allowing fine-grained control over GPU resources and gives developers the ability to optimise memory and thread management, potentially achieving very high performance. This, however, requires expertise in GPU architecture, is time-consuming and results in code that is harder to maintain and modify. Because some APIs are vendor specific (e.g., CUDA), codes using them will not be portable.

Compiler directives: GPUs can also be programmed with directive-based frameworks like OpenMP and OpenACC. These provide a high-level approach, where developers annotate code regions with pragmas to offload computation to GPUs. This approach has the advantage of only requiring minimal changes to the code and is usually portable across platforms and architectures. The main disadvantage is that performance tuning is often left to the compiler, and it might not be easy to effectively exploit all GPU capabilities, like warp/thread optimisation. However, this is an area where improvements are expected, with recent and future standards providing better memory and warp/thread control.

Performance portability frameworks: Several programming frameworks have been developed to provide abstractions for parallelism and data management, enabling portability across CPUs, GPUs, and other architectures (e.g., Kokkos, RAJA, etc). These frameworks are usually written in C++ and they abstract away low-level GPU details, simplifying programming and reducing vendor

lock-in. They usually provide good performance across the supported architectures and integrate well with C++ codes, but they require developers to learn the framework-specific APIs and their integration with Fortran codes can be cumbersome.

Domain-specific languages: These are languages and tools designed to abstract domain-specific operations and automatically generate code suitable to run either on CPUs or GPUs. This allows developers to focus on domain-level concepts rather than hardware and to produce portable code. A prominent example of a DSL in the area of climate modelling is Psychone, which was developed by the UK MetOffice as part of their Next Generation Modelling Systems Programme.

Data

A. Recent and Future Trends

High-performance data is rapidly becoming as critical as high-performance computing within the scientific and research landscape. We are currently witnessing explosive growth in data volumes across Earth and environmental sciences, particularly in climate modelling. This surge is driven by advances in sensor technology, computational simulations, and the increasing adoption of AI and machine learning (ML) methods across disciplines. As data volumes continue to climb, so does the need for robust data strategies that can manage, scale, ensure quality and accessibility, and support optimised, large-scale workflows on HPC platforms.

Working with large climate model outputs is increasingly complex as users need to access, analyse and combine data across multiple platforms. Transferring terabyte- or petabyte-scale data between HPC and other environments is often impractical. Bandwidth, cost, and storage constraints limit what can realistically be moved or processed locally. These issues make it difficult for downstream users, such as decision-makers or researchers from other fields, to incorporate ACCESS outputs into their workflows.

Growing data volumes also put increased pressure on storage, access, and workflow performance. I/O bottlenecks remain a significant limitation when running on thousands of cores and processing terabytes of data. Addressing these challenges requires more efficient data-handling practices across HPC and cloud platforms, including improved layouts, chunking, caching, built-in compression, and downscaling within the modelling pipelines. ML-driven methods also offer new possibilities for automated data compression, quality control, and summarisation. These shifts are prompting a re-evaluation of formats and structures used to store and access climate data. Traditional formats such as netCDF and HDF remain foundational due to their embedded metadata handling and broad compatibility with scientific tools but do have some limitations. As analysis moves toward cloud or hybrid (HPC-cloud) environments, cloud-optimised formats such as Zarr² are becoming increasingly popular. These developments highlight the need for formats that support scalable, cross-platform analysis, while reducing the burden on users working with ever-larger climate outputs.

Data interoperability adds further complexity, with ACCESS model outputs requiring several post-processing stages before data can be easily compared or integrated with other data sources. The one major exception is output that is specifically curated for the Couple Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)³ activities, which follows strict data and metadata standards. In contrast, datasets not prepared for CMIP can vary considerably in structure and completeness. While current ACCESS outputs generally follow community standards such as CF-Conventions, the required post-processing often leads to inconsistencies across model components and generated data. In practice, this creates barriers to combining ACCESS outputs with other model datasets or observational products, with users frequently encountering variability and gaps across metadata, naming conventions, and file structures before analysis can even begin.

² <https://zarr.dev/>

³ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/>

B. Opportunities and Challenges

Improving the quality and usability of ACCESS datasets requires adopting data management best practices, including FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics). Embedding these principles directly within the modelling workflows, rather than relying on post-processing, offers an opportunity to uplift consistency and reduce user burden. Achieving this will require a unified approach across ACCESS releases, including common vocabularies, naming conventions, provenance standards, and systematic versioning. Where possible, it is also critical to align these practices with international best practices and initiatives, such as CMIP and CODATA's Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF).

Improving I/O performance and data-handling efficiency, identified as key pressure points in the trends above, also represents a major opportunity for ACCESS-NRI. This includes modernising data layouts, adopting parallel I/O strategies, and integrating compression and downscaling within modelling pipelines. These advancements would reduce data movement, improve workflow scalability, and support more efficient analysis across HPC and cloud environments.

AI-ready data is becoming increasingly important as machine learning gains momentum in climate applications. For ML workflows to operate efficiently, data must be well-structured, fast to ingest, and supported by machine-readable metadata. Efficient caching, compression, and access-pattern optimisation are essential to avoid I/O bottlenecks when training large models. The Croissant metadata framework from MLCommons⁴ is one potential standard to watch, offering a structured, portable way to describe datasets for ML and supporting greater automation and reproducibility across diverse environments.

Finally, reducing barriers to entry for the broader community is essential. Many researchers and decision-making groups lack the capability to work directly with HPC-scale datasets or move them across platforms. Providing user-friendly discovery tools, federated catalogues, and compute-to-data environments, where analysis occurs close to the data, will be critical to enabling widespread use of ACCESS outputs. Adoption of consistent data practices and shared infrastructure across institutions will allow the community to work more efficiently and unlock greater value from Australia's climate modelling investments.

⁴ <https://mlcommons.org/working-groups/data/croissant>

Machine Learning for Climate and Weather

A. Recent developments

Recent advances in algorithms and hardware have made machine learning (ML) a technology with the potential to significantly transform many areas of scientific research. This is particularly evident in climate and weather modelling, where ML techniques are being applied to a wide variety of problems and opening new avenues for research. In this section, we discuss the current state-of-the-art of machine learning in the context of improving the understanding and predictions of weather and climate, and their impact on socio-economic human systems.

The appropriate machine learning solutions to tackle a given problem in climate and weather science depend on two things: the time horizon of interest and the degree to which one has fundamental physical laws of nature that one can rely upon. This is illustrated in Figure 2, where from left to right we increase from short weather timescales to long climatic ones, with progressively less statistically independent samples available.

This typically means that feasible ML approaches need to be simpler with less parameters for climate applications as opposed to weather. The vertical axis goes from purely physical systems at the bottom, to the impact of the weather and climate on socio-economic factors at the top. In the former, ML applications can be designed to exploit our knowledge of the physical system. In the latter regime, ML approaches are reliant purely upon the input weather / climate (and socio-economic) data. Prototypical science problems are listed within each quadrant.

Figure 2: Characteristics of ML applications depending upon time horizon and fundamental knowledge of the underlying dynamics.

There are many ML approaches and developments relevant to each of the four quadrants. One of the most disruptive has been the development of increasingly sophisticated AI architectures for atmospheric modeling in particular. Notably, models such as Pangu-Weather, GenCast, GraphCast, and FourCastNet leverage various methods to capture complex dependencies in the input datasets. These advances have contributed to the high performance of AI-based forecasting systems, in some cases surpassing traditional numerical weather prediction. At this stage, their defensible applications sit within the physical weather timescales in the bottom left-hand quadrant of figure 2.

There is ongoing research to further develop and verify their suitability in longer timescale climate applications. However, this sophistication comes at a cost. Modern AI models require significant computational resources, including multiple GPUs with large memory capacities and extended training times.

B. Opportunities and Challenges

Machine learning is transforming the way most science is done, driving rapid gains in fundamental productivity of scientific research. Australia has a unique opportunity to build a vibrant machine learning research community for weather and climate. Seizing this opportunity will empower researchers, institutions, and industry to achieve breakthroughs with direct relevance to Australian needs.

There are significant factors which distinguish the Australian geographical region, including sources of observational data, a unique land mass, and its climate. The specific regional challenges are also substantial: unique exposure to fire, flood, drought (sometimes all at once), tropical cyclones, and climate impacts on sensitive locations such as agricultural zones. These differences and unique challenges mean it is not possible to solely rely on international developments. ML models developed overseas must be adapted, retrained, fine-tuned, or even redesigned for Australian use. Without this localisation, there is a risk of missing critical insights and tailored solutions. By leading in these areas, Australia can also offer scientific leadership to neighboring countries and communities across the Asia Pacific (APAC) region.

However, two interlinked challenges must be addressed: ensuring access to the right tools and fostering an effective, collaborative community. Currently, neither is fully optimised for accelerating innovation in Australia's weather and climate research sector.

To enable impactful research, Australian scientists need access to the right tools:

- Regionally relevant datasets: Large, multi-terabyte data collections, which are easy to load in ML-capable frameworks for processing.
- Adequate compute resources: Access to sufficient GPU capacity to support large-scale, cutting-edge ML research.
- Empowering software environments and information resources: Platforms, libraries, documentation, and training materials that make it easy for students, researchers, and educators to adopt new ML methodologies.
- Equally important is the creation of a strong, connected network of people who can collaborate and share expertise: Open collaboration through shared computing resources and tools that make it easy for researchers to work together on high-value scientific challenges.

- Clear definition of important scientific problems, with worked examples, so that new participants can quickly become productive and aligned with the community's goals.
- Active communication channels to foster dialogue and collaboration between experts, students, and those adopting ML for the first time.
- A welcoming, supportive culture that prioritises excellence, inclusivity, and results.
- Strong connections with scientific subcommunities undergoing rapid transformation, enabling cross-pollination of ideas and shared solutions.

Once the required compute, tools and community are in-place, Australian scientists will be in a better position to undertake innovative research, and to contribute leadership and valuable solutions to the broader region.

Conclusions

The HPC, cloud computing, data, and machine-learning landscapes are currently undergoing transformative changes that have the potential to seriously disrupt the field of climate and weather modelling. GPUs are now an essential part of the HPC and cloud landscapes and will be part of it for the foreseeable future. At the same time, data volumes and storage requirements are rapidly increasing, increasing the need to maintain data quality, consistency, and accessibility at the petabyte scale. The application of machine learning to climate and weather has opened new avenues of research, and emerging ML-based models are increasingly complementing and, in some cases, challenging traditional physics-based approaches.

These shifts present challenges and opportunities that cannot be ignored by the ACCESS community, at the risk of not being able to stay at the forefront of climate and weather research. For example, porting the ACCESS models to run efficiently on GPUs will require considerable resources and close collaboration with code owners, but also has the potential to accelerate the existing models and to enable higher-resolution models. Such advancements will, in turn, drive further increases in data production and place greater pressure on I/O performance, storage systems, and workflow scalability. Harnessing the full promise of machine-learning will also require well-curated datasets, AI-ready datasets, modern software environments, scalable compute and, more importantly, a thriving community of scientists and software engineers in Australia.

To address these challenges effectively, several key priorities emerge:

- Prepare for next generation HPC by accelerating GPU-readiness across ACCESS models and expanding GPU capacity for emerging ML workflows.
- Embed consistent metadata, provenance, and unified data specifications directly within modelling workflows, reducing reliance on post-processing, and supporting long-term FAIR and CARE compliance across all ACCESS data outputs.
- Improve I/O performance and data handling efficiency to enable scalable analysis and ML-ready datasets.
- Lower barriers to data discovery, analysis, and ML adoption by providing user-friendly catalogues and community-oriented tools and training.
- Build an active, collaborative community in the field of ML for climate and weather by connecting researchers, developers, and data scientists across Australia.

Because all these challenges are transversal to the field and to the Australian research community, a coherent strategy involving all the stakeholders will be essential.

We therefore recommend that ACCESS-NRI develop and publish a comprehensive strategy document to guide future activities. With its mandate to support Australian science, prepare for future changes, and build a connected community across academia, government, science, industry and society, ACCESS-NRI is ideally placed to play a pivotal role in coordinating and implementing such strategy in partnership with the research community.

Appendix A

GPU-Readiness of ACCESS Models

The ACCESS models are usually built by combining separate domain-specific components (e.g., atmosphere, ocean, etc.) with a coupler. The coupler and each model component are in turn composed of one or more software packages, each developed and maintained by a different community. Next is a list of the most relevant software packages used by the latest generation of ACCESS models and a brief assessment of their level of GPU-readiness.

UM/LFRic

The current generation of ACCESS models uses the UM for the atmosphere component. Although the UM has no GPU capabilities, its successor, LFRic, has been developed taking into account new HPC architectures and will therefore include GPU support. The UK MetOffice has plans to start using LFRic for operational weather forecasting sometime in 2025, but this timeline could still change, and it is unclear when the code will be ready to be used as a component of the ACCESS models.

MOM6

MOM6 is the ocean component used in the ACCESS models. Currently it includes no GPU support, but the MOM6 developers have started working on this. This project is still in its early stages, and it is difficult to estimate when the code will be GPU ready.

CICE6

A small part of CICE, the sea-ice component, was rewritten to a shared memory model and is therefore able to run on GPU. There are currently no plans to port other parts of the code.

WAVEWATCH III

The WAVEWATCH III wave modelling framework is a recent addition to ACCESS. No GPU support is available in the code, but work is currently underway by the UK MetOffice to investigate the feasibility of porting the code to GPUs and to scope for necessary optimisations and code refactoring.

CABLE

CABLE is the ACCESS land model component and currently has no GPU support. Although there are currently no plans to port it to GPUs, it should be noted that, when using the ACCESS models, CABLE is usually only responsible for a very small fraction of the total computing time.

ISSM

ISSM has recently been adopted as the ice sheet component of the ACCESS models. No GPU support is currently available, but the developers have started to study the porting of specific algorithms used in the code to GPUs with promising results.